

User Feedback - Survey (Participants)

This survey aims to assess the level of satisfaction of participants with the hackathon (test & development) and gather feedback for improving processes, aiming for the creation of an 'on demand' demonstration of Mondaecus. Future demonstrations are expected to be a demonstration, a training exercise and at same time a workshop dedicated to a real 'translation need' of the organization receiving the demonstration of Mondaecus. The Hackathon output is the creation of a guideline on how to prepare and deliver such exercise and the survey supports its refinement.

Part A – The Hackathon Event & Procedures

1. How clear were the objectives of the hackathon? (1–5)
2. Was the balance between translation and review adequate? (Yes/No/Partially)
3. How did you find the collaboration with other participants? (Very good / Good / Mixed / Difficult)
4. Did the moderation help the group's workflow? (Yes/No/Partially)
5. Were the time slots sufficient for the tasks? (Yes/No)
6. What aspects of the hackathon worked best? (Open)
7. What aspects should be improved in future editions? (Open)
8. How satisfied are you with the organization of the event? (1–5)

Part B – The Mondaecus Platform

1. How easy was it to access and log in? (1–5)
2. Did you face any technical issues? If yes, please specify. (Open)
3. How user-friendly was the interface? (1–5)
4. Which functionalities supported your work most effectively? (Comments/selection)
5. How well did the platform support collaboration in your group? (1–5)
6. Do you think the platform is scalable for larger groups and more complex tasks? (Yes/No/Not sure)
7. Would you recommend Mondaecus for other collaborative translation exercises? (Yes/No/With improvements)
8. What improvements would you suggest for the platform? (Open)